

Patnai 23, where bud length was generally longer and showed a distinct lengthening trend with increased cutting. This is attributed largely to a varietal difference and to a variety × cutting

height interaction in respect to bud length.

Varietal differences in ratoon tillers per plant were not significant, but the effect of cutting height and the

interaction effect were. A higher cut produced a higher number of ratoon tillers. Bud length was not influenced by viable bud number. □

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

GRAIN QUALITY

Demonstration of rice parboiling using an improved wood stove

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The initial demonstration of parboiling of rice among growers of the Zio River Irrigated Perimeter in Togo, held by APP in 1985, did not result in adoption of the practice even though several advantages were clear: a 6% increase in milling yield, cleaner and fewer broken grains, and less insect damage during storage. Nonadoption was attributed to poor selection of participants and lack of follow-up.

The APP agronomist felt that there were enough potential benefits to warrant reintroduction of the technique. A brief technical bulletin explaining the process and its benefits was distributed to extension agents. The targets selected this time were APP clients who were life-long residents of the village of Assome. The program included a fuel-saving wood stove and fuel wood production using *Leucaena leucocephala*.

Three separate demonstrations covered 1) the building of mud stoves, 2) parboiling, and 3) cooking and taste tests. The first showed the need to produce fuel wood as well as save fuel. Planting *Leucaena* adjacent to the drying floor and warehouse was suggested.

Parboiling was done in a modified metal drum. The parboiled rice gave a milling yield of 69% versus 62% for the nonparboiled.

In the third demonstration, held on a

market day, women were invited to taste parboiled and nonparboiled rice with a sauce. They expressed preference for parboiled rice.

Influence of planting date on milling performance of rice varieties under delayed harvesting

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The evaluation of advanced lines for milling quality by comparing samples harvested at 20-25% moisture content with those left standing in the field 10-15 additional days is normal practice in the rice breeding program at CIAT. Such an approach is expected to predict milling performance at the farm level accurately.

We studied the milling performance of varieties CICA8 and Oryzica 1 for seven planting dates in Palmira, Colombia, during Feb 1985-Aug 1986. Plantings were simultaneous on all but the third planting date, when CICA8 was planted 1 wk earlier to obtain simultaneous maturity. Two samples of 1 kg of rough rice each were taken twice for each variety and planting time — when grain moisture was 20-25%, and 12-15 d later. Milling evaluations were done using standard McCill laboratory equipment.

The effect of delayed harvest on the head rice yields varied according to planting date (see figure). CICA8 showed no reduction in three of the seven evaluations, and Oryzica 1 in four.

A typical farmer who plants 1 ha to rice and grows 2 crops/yr could realize \$300-400 more profit by adopting parboiling. □

Head rice yield of 2 rice varieties harvested at 20-25% moisture content and delayed for 12-15 d, for 7 planting dates. Cali, Colombia, 1985-86.

Screening rice genotypes for tolerance for delayed harvest in the field would thus require consideration of environmental effects. □

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